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The Impact of Carbon Pricing on the Performance of Energy Firms: A Comparative Analysis Between Renewable and Traditional Energy

UNGAR Kevin^{1,*} and OPREAN-STAN Camelia²

¹Lucian Blaga University of Sibiu, Romania; kevin.ungar@ulbsibiu.ro; <https://orcid.org/0009-0007-3372-9374>

²Lucian Blaga University of Sibiu, Romania; camelia.oprean@ulbsibiu.ro; <https://orcid.org/0000-0003-3492-2401>

* Correspondence: kevin.ungar@ulbsibiu.ro

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Abstract: *This study examines how carbon pricing and key macroeconomic factors influence the stock performance of energy firms, with a comparative focus on renewable versus traditional energy sectors. The analysis contrasts the European Renewable Energy Index (ERIX) with traditional energy stocks included in the MSCI index to evaluate differential impacts. A dataset of 1,279 daily observations is utilized, and a sequential econometric methodology—comprising OLS, GLS, WLS, and final GLSAR regression—is employed to control for non-stationarity and multicollinearity, thereby ensuring robust inference. The findings reveal that carbon pricing – proxied by EU carbon futures – is a significant driver of renewable energy stock performance, while its effect on traditional energy firms is positive but markedly smaller. In contrast, macroeconomic variables (interest rates, inflation, GDP) and even EU carbon allowance volumes exhibit limited or no statistically significant impact on either sector's returns. These results suggest that renewable energy stocks are more sensitive to carbon market expectations than their conventional counterparts. The study offers important implications for both policymakers and investors: it underscores the policy relevance of carbon markets in incentivizing clean energy (supporting decarbonization goals) and informs investment strategies by highlighting that portfolio exposure to renewables versus traditional energy should be calibrated considering carbon price dynamics. This comparative evidence contributes to sustainable finance literature and can guide sector-specific portfolio management under evolving carbon pricing regimes.*

Keywords: *Carbon pricing; Renewable energy; Stock performance; Sustainable finance; Macroeconomic factors*

1. Introduction

The objective of this study is to evaluate the impact of carbon pricing on the financial performance of energy sector firms, comparing renewable energy companies against traditional (fossil-based) energy companies. This question is important in the context of global decarbonization efforts and the rise of sustainable finance. As countries adopt stricter climate policies, carbon pricing has emerged as a key policy tool, incentivizing low-carbon practices and innovation while internalizing the environmental costs of emissions (Mengesha & Roy, 2025). Financial markets are increasingly sensitive to such climate policies; investors now actively account for carbon risks and climate policy uncertainty in their portfolio decisions (Caporale et al., 2023). Understanding whether carbon pricing affects clean energy stocks differently from conventional energy stocks is thus critical. It can shed light on how climate policies drive capital allocation in the energy industry and inform both policymakers designing carbon markets and investors managing climate-related risks.

This study leverages a unique dataset of European markets, comprising 1,279 daily observations that include the European Renewable Energy Total Return Index (ERIX) and a corresponding MSCI energy index representing traditional energy firms. The ERIX index serves as a proxy for Europe's clean energy sector, tracking major companies in wind, solar, biomass, hydropower and related renewable industries (Caporale et al., 2023). We pair this with a broad MSCI index of traditional energy companies (largely oil & gas and utilities) to enable a sectoral comparison. In addition to stock indices, our dataset integrates carbon market variables – notably EU carbon futures prices and the volume of EU Emission Allowances (EUA) auctions – alongside macroeconomic indicators (interest rates, inflation, and GDP) for the European Union. Focusing on Europe is justified by its climate policy leadership: the EU pioneered carbon pricing through the EU Emissions Trading System (EU ETS) (in operation since 2005) and set global benchmarks in emissions reduction and renewable energy deployment (Mengesha & Roy, 2025). This regional context provides a mature carbon market and active renewable sector, offering an ideal setting to study carbon price pass-through effects on different energy industries.

Our work makes several contributions to the literature. First, it addresses a gap regarding sectoral asymmetries in carbon price pass-through. Few prior studies explicitly compare how carbon pricing affects clean energy versus traditional energy stock performance, and existing evidence has been mixed (Jiang et al., 2023). By directly contrasting the ERIX and MSCI energy indices, we provide new insights into whether “green” firms benefit more (or suffer less) from carbon price increases than “brown” (carbon-intensive) firms. Second, we combine high-frequency financial data with policy and macroeconomic variables, an approach that melds daily market information with regulatory signals. Many earlier analyses have relied on coarser frequencies or limited covariates – for example, using weekly data without broader economic controls (Caporale et al., 2023) – potentially overlooking short-term market adjustments. In contrast, our daily-frequency analysis captures immediate stock market reactions to carbon price fluctuations and controls for concurrent economic conditions. Third, we improve econometric robustness by employing a Generalized Least Squares with Autoregressive errors (GLSAR) model. Prior studies often used static OLS or VAR frameworks focused on average effects (Jiang et al., 2023), without fully accounting for issues like autocorrelation in residuals or time-varying volatility. In our analysis, the GLSAR technique substantially mitigates serial correlation and enhances the reliability of coefficient estimates. By addressing these methodological challenges (stationarity, multicollinearity, heteroskedasticity, and autocorrelation), we ensure that the estimated impact of carbon pricing on each sector is both unbiased and efficient. Overall, the study offers a more nuanced and credible assessment of how carbon market signals transmit to equity values in different energy industries.

The remainder of the paper is structured as follows. Section 2 reviews recent literature on carbon pricing and energy stock performance, highlighting both supportive and contradictory findings. Section 3 describes the data and methodology, including model specifications and diagnostic approaches. Section 4 presents the empirical results, comparing the effects of carbon futures and other variables on renewable versus traditional energy stock indices. Section 5 concludes with a summary of insights and suggestions for future research.

2. Literature Review

Recent empirical studies generally support the view that carbon pricing can materially influence energy sector stock performance, with renewable energy firms often showing greater sensitivity. For instance, Caporale et al. (2023) examine stock market reactions under climate policy scenarios and find that effective climate policies lead to higher stock prices for renewable (“new energy”) companies, along with increased spillovers between renewable and fossil-fuel stock indices. This suggests that stricter carbon policies – which raise the cost of emissions – tend to favor clean energy firms in relative terms. Similarly, a quantile-causality analysis by Jiang et al. (2023) reveals a significant bidirectional relationship between carbon prices and clean energy stock returns. Their results indicate that fluctuations in carbon pricing substantially affect renewable energy equity performance, especially during extreme market conditions (bullish or bearish periods). Evidence from U.S. markets aligns with these findings: studies have observed that rising carbon prices correlate with improved clean energy stock returns, and carbon price shocks can exert dynamic influences on green energy asset values (Jiang et al., 2023). Together, these works underscore that carbon market signals are quickly absorbed by

investors in renewable energy, making this sector's stocks particularly responsive to changes in carbon pricing regimes.

On the other hand, several studies have reported weak, negative, or no significant linkages between carbon pricing and energy stock performance. Early evidence by Kumar et al. (2012), Dutta (2017) and others found no statistically significant Granger-causal effect of EU carbon price changes on U.S. clean energy stock indices, implying that carbon market fluctuations did not translate into immediate renewable stock movement in certain contexts. Other research points to an inverse or muted relationship: for example, some volatility-spillover analyses suggest that carbon prices may actually be influenced by renewable stock trends (i.e. EU carbon allowances being “spillover receivers” from clean energy markets) rather than driving them (Hanif et al., 2021; Tiwari et al., 2022). In such cases, the direction of causality is reversed or diffused, and carbon pricing itself has limited direct impact on equity returns. Moreover, a number of studies have found carbon-related variables to affect only the risk or volatility of energy firms' stocks, without a clear effect on mean returns. These mixed results highlight that the carbon price–stock performance nexus is not unequivocal; it may depend on factors like region, timeframe, and model specification. Negative impacts on traditional high-emission firms have been documented in event studies (e.g. sudden carbon policy tightenings can depress stock prices of carbon-intensive companies) (Hengge, 2023), yet translating those effects into consistently observable advantages for renewables has proven challenging in some analyses. This divergence in findings motivates a closer examination using refined data and methods.

A key reason for the above inconsistencies lies in methodological and data limitations in prior research. Many earlier studies employ static models or average-effect approaches that might overlook dynamic adjustments and feedback in the carbon–energy relationship (Jiang et al., 2023). Additionally, the frequency of observation and scope of variables used in previous work have often been constrained. Some analyses rely on low-frequency (e.g. weekly or monthly) data and a narrow set of variables, which may smooth over important high-frequency interactions (Caporale et al., 2023). In such setups, issues like autocorrelation in residuals and omitted variable bias (from missing macroeconomic controls) can obscure true causal effects. Recognizing these shortcomings, recent literature has called for more granular and robust approaches – for instance, using daily data, longer sample horizons, and incorporating macro-financial indicators – to better isolate the impact of carbon pricing on stock markets (Caporale et al., 2023). Our study responds to these gaps by adopting a daily-frequency dataset covering multiple years and key EU-wide variables, and by applying a GLSAR model that explicitly addresses autocorrelation. This generalized least squares with autoregressive error approach improves upon ordinary least squares by accounting for serial correlation in stock returns, thereby providing more reliable inference on the relationship in question. By mitigating autocorrelation and controlling for macroeconomic confounders, the analysis gains precision in estimating how carbon futures and allowance metrics transmit to renewable and traditional energy stock performance. This enhanced methodological rigor allows us to contribute clearer evidence to the debate, helping reconcile some of the divergent findings in the literature and offering a more solid basis for policy and investment considerations.

3. Methodology

3.1. Data Collection and Processing

To build a comprehensive dataset for our analysis, we gathered data from several websites. Our dependent variables, which capture the stock prices of energy companies, include:

- European Renewable Energy Total Return (ERIX) – sourced from Investing.com (n.y.a);
- MSCI Europe Energy (MIEU0EN00PEU) – sourced from Investing.com (n.y.b).

For the independent variables, we collected:

- Carbon Emissions Futures - Mar 25 (CFI2H5) – sourced from Investing.com (n.y.c);
- Allowance Actioned or Sold EUAs/EUAAs – sourced from European Environment Agency (n.y.).

Additionally, we included control variables to account for broader economic factors:

- European Union GDP – sourced from Macrotrends (n.y.);
- Inflation Rate in the European Union – sourced from FRED (n.y.) and YCharts (n.y.);
- Eurozone Interest Rate Decision – sourced from Investing.com.

Our selection of indicators was driven by the need to capture both sector-specific dynamics and broader economic influences. ERIX and MSCI Europe Energy were chosen as they directly reflect the performance of energy companies, encompassing both renewable and conventional sectors. The independent variables (Carbon Emissions Futures and Allowance Actioned or Sold EUAs/EUAAs) offer valuable insights into market expectations regarding carbon emissions and the trading volumes of carbon certificates. Specifically, Carbon Emissions Futures capture current prices while also integrating future market sentiment, and the EUA-related data serve as a measure of regulatory market activity. Moreover, by including control variables such as European Union GDP, the Inflation Rate, and the Eurozone Interest Rate Decision, our models account for macroeconomic conditions that could influence market performance. These widely recognized benchmarks provide a robust context for understanding the interplay between energy market dynamics and the broader economic environment.

Since the datasets collected from different websites were originally reported at varying frequencies (daily, monthly, and annually), we standardized all data to a daily frequency covering January 2, 2019, to December 29, 2023. This process involved converting date fields into a consistent datetime format and ensuring that numerical columns were appropriately typed. For datasets with lower frequencies (monthly or annual), we applied the Last Observation Carried Forward (LOCF) method to fill any gaps. We chose LOCF because macroeconomic indicators, such as European Union GDP, the inflation rate, and Eurozone interest rate decisions, do not fluctuate significantly daily. Carrying forward the last available observation prevents the introduction of artificial volatility, preserves the underlying trend, and ensures continuity in our daily dataset. In contrast, datasets already available at a daily frequency were left unaltered.

After preprocessing each dataset to address unique formatting and reporting differences, we merged all variables into a unified table using the common 'Date' column. It is important to note that the daily datasets (such as ERIX, MSCI Europe Energy, and Carbon Emissions Futures) naturally presented some missing values due to market holidays or data reporting inconsistencies. To ensure a consistent and complete dataset for our regression analysis, we employed the `dropna()` function to remove any rows containing missing values. The final dataset used in the multiple linear regression model comprised 1,279 observations per variable.

3.2. Models

This research utilized the Ordinary Least Squares (OLS) model (Burton, 2021), implemented in Python via the “statsmodels.api” library. The dataset was pre-processed to isolate the independent variable from the dependent variables. Subsequently, the OLS model was trained twice, with each training iteration using one of the two dependent variables: European Renewable Energy Total Return (ERIX) and MSCI Europe Energy (MSCI). The mathematical representation of the linear regression model for each observation i (where $i = 1, 2, \dots, n$) is given by:

$$Y_i = \beta_0 + \beta_1 X_{1,i} + \beta_2 X_{2,i} + \beta_3 X_{3,i} + \beta_4 X_{4,i} + \beta_5 X_{5,i} + \epsilon_i \quad (1)$$

where:

- Y_i : represents the observed value of the dependent variable at observation i . For our research, Y_i could be the stock index value (ERIX or MSCI) on day i .
- β_0 : is the intercept term. It represents the expected value of Y when all predictors X_1, X_2, \dots, X_5 are zero.
- β_j (for $j=1, \dots, 5$): are the slope coefficients. Each β_j measures the expected change in Y given a one-unit change in the predictor X_j , holding all other variables constant.
- $X_{j,i}$: is the observed value of predictor j for observation i . For example, $X_{1,i}$ is the Carbon Emissions Futures value on day i .

- ϵ_i : the error term for observation i , capturing all factors not included in the model (it represents the "noise" or unexplained variation in the data). We assume these errors are independently and identically distributed with mean 0 and constant variance σ^2 : $\epsilon_i \sim N(0, \sigma^2)$.

In the OLS model in Python, the results are presented under the following assumptions:

- **Linearity:** the relationship between the dependent variable and the predictors is linear. This implies that a change in a predictor variable result in a proportional change in the dependent variable.
- **Independence:** the errors ϵ_i are independent across observations. Therefore, there is no autocorrelation of the residuals, meaning that past residuals cannot influence future ones. Autocorrelation can lead to underestimation of standard errors, making statistical tests unreliable.
- **Homoscedasticity:** the errors have constant variance, $\text{Var}(\epsilon_i) = \sigma^2$ for all i . Consequently, heteroscedasticity is not present.
- **No perfect multicollinearity:** the predictors are not perfectly correlated, ensuring that $X^T X$ is invertible. The predictor variables are represented as columns within the design matrix, denoted as X . Perfect multicollinearity occurs when one or more of these predictor columns can be expressed as an exact linear combination of the others.
- **Normality of errors:** for inference purposes, the errors are assumed to be normally distributed. This assumption can be relaxed for large samples due to the Central Limit Theorem. While the Ordinary Least Squares (OLS) method, commonly used to estimate these coefficients, does not inherently require normally distributed errors, distributional assumptions are necessary for probabilistic statements about the estimated coefficients.

In addition to the assumptions, stationarity is a crucial consideration, particularly when dealing with time-series data. The assumption of independence of errors is closely related to stationarity, as non-stationary time series are prone to autocorrelation, which violates the independence assumption. A stationary time series exhibits statistical properties that remain constant over time. Non-stationary time series can introduce autocorrelation, invalidating the independence of errors assumption. To address non-stationarity, we employed the Augmented Dickey-Fuller test. We also assessed multicollinearity using the Variance Inflation Factor. Both issues were mitigated by computing the rolling average and applying the first difference to variables with daily and monthly frequencies, and by using the percentage change method for annual variables. However, despite this preprocessing, residual autocorrelation and heteroscedasticity were still present.

Since the OLS model did not prove sufficient to assess the impact of the independent variables on the dependent ones, due to violations of key OLS assumptions, we tested for heteroscedasticity using the Breusch-Pagan test and for serial correlation using the Durbin-Watson and Breusch-Godfrey tests. The results indicated significant heteroscedasticity and serial correlation in the residuals, which violate the assumptions of homoscedasticity and independent errors. Given these issues, we transitioned from OLS to Generalized Least Squares (GLS), which accounts for these violations by incorporating a structured variance-covariance matrix.

The GLS model (Phillips & Park, 1988) is an extension of OLS that addresses the presence of heteroscedasticity (non-constant variance of errors) and autocorrelation (correlated residuals). Unlike OLS, which assumes homoscedastic and uncorrelated errors, GLS provides more efficient and unbiased estimates when these assumptions are violated.

The GLS model modifies the standard OLS equation:

$$Y = X\beta + \epsilon \quad (2)$$

where:

- Y is a vector (a column of numbers) representing the observed values of the dependent variable. Each element in Y corresponds to an observation.

- X represents the design matrix, containing the values of the independent variables. Each row of X corresponds to an observation, and each column corresponds to an independent variable.
- β is a vector of the regression coefficients. These coefficients represent the impact of each independent variable on the dependent variable. GLS aims to estimate these coefficients.
- ϵ is the error term vector. It represents the difference between the observed values of Y and the values predicted by the model. This is where the crucial difference between OLS and GLS lies.

Then the GLS assumes that the error term follows:

$$E[\epsilon\epsilon^T] = \sigma^2\Omega \quad (3)$$

where Ω (Omega) is the covariance matrix of the errors. If Ω is unknown, Feasible Generalized Least Squares (FGLS) is used, where Ω is estimated from the data rather than assumed to be known.

To address heteroscedasticity and autocorrelation, GLS transforms the model by pre-multiplying both sides of Equation (2) by $\Omega^{-1/2}$:

$$\left(\Omega^{-\frac{1}{2}}Y\right) = \left(\Omega^{-\frac{1}{2}}X\right)\beta + \left(\Omega^{-\frac{1}{2}}\epsilon\right) \quad (4)$$

This transformation ensures that the transformed errors ($\Omega^{-1/2}\epsilon$) have constant variance and are uncorrelated, thereby satisfying the standard OLS assumptions.

By incorporating Ω , GLS adjusts for nonconstant error variances. If certain observations exhibit higher variability (and thus are less reliable), GLS down-weights them, yielding more efficient estimates than OLS.

In the context of our research, GLS provided a more robust framework by adjusting for the identified violations (heteroscedasticity and autocorrelation), which were detected using the Breusch-Pagan, Durbin-Watson, and Breusch-Godfrey tests. However, it was insufficient to fully account for the underlying structure of the errors. Consequently, we adopted the Weighted Least Squares (WLS) method, which explicitly accounts for heteroscedasticity by assigning weights to each observation, thereby improving the efficiency of the estimates.

The WLS model (Cohen & Migliorati, 2017) modifies the standard regression equation by introducing a weighting matrix “ W ”, where each weight corresponds to the inverse of the variance of the error term associated with that observation. The weighted regression equation is given by:

$$WY = WX\beta + W\epsilon, \quad (5)$$

where W is a diagonal matrix defined as:

$$W = \text{diag}\left(\frac{1}{\sqrt{\sigma_1^2}}, \frac{1}{\sqrt{\sigma_2^2}}, \dots, \frac{1}{\sqrt{\sigma_n^2}}\right) \quad (6)$$

In this formulation each observation is assigned a weight inversely proportional to the estimated variance of its residuals, ensuring that observations with higher variance contribute less to the estimation. Unlike GLS, which assumes a known error covariance structure, WLS directly estimates the heteroscedasticity function, making it a more flexible approach when dealing with non-constant variance.

The motivation for adopting WLS over GLS was driven by the nature of heteroscedasticity observed in our dataset. While GLS incorporates a general covariance structure, it assumes the existence of an underlying correlation model for errors. In contrast, WLS allowed us to directly correct for the variance disparities across observations, leading to more precise coefficient estimates and valid statistical inference. However, the persistence of heteroscedasticity and autocorrelation in the residuals, even after Weighted Least Squares (WLS) adjustments, compromised our ability to accurately assess the impact of independent variables (X) on dependent variables (Y). Obtaining unbiased coefficient estimates with reliable standard errors, crucial for our research objectives, was significantly hindered by these violations. Consequently, an explicit correction for autocorrelation was required. So, we implemented

the Feasible Generalized Least Squares (FGLS) utilizing the Generalized Least Squares with Autoregressive Errors (GLSAR) method.

The GLSAR method (McKinney et al., 2011) extends GLS by explicitly modeling autocorrelation in the error term, typically assuming an autoregressive process of order p (denoted as AR(p)). This means that the errors are not independently distributed but instead follow a structured dependency over time.

To capture the serial correlation, we assume the errors follow an AR(1) process:

$$\epsilon_t = \hat{\rho}\epsilon_{t-1} + u_t \quad (7)$$

where:

- ϵ_t represents the error term (or residual) at time t . It's the difference between the observed value and the predicted value of the dependent variable at that time point.
- $\hat{\rho}$ is the estimated autocorrelation coefficient, obtained from the OLS residuals. It measures the strength of the linear relationship between the error term at time t and the error term at the previous time point, $t-1$.
- u_t : is a white noise error term with mean zero and constant variance ($u_t \sim N(0, \sigma^2)$).

After we obtained estimated $\hat{\rho}$ from the OLS residuals, we transformed the original model to remove the autocorrelation:

- For $t = 1$

$$Y_1^* = Y_1, \quad X_1^* = X_1 \quad (8)$$

These equations mean that the first observations of both the dependent and independent variables remain unchanged in the transformed model. No transformation is applied to the first data point because there is no previous time point $t-1$ to use for the adjustment.

- For $t \geq 2$

$$\begin{aligned} Y_t^* &= Y_t - \hat{\rho}Y_{t-1} \\ X_t^* &= X_t - \hat{\rho}X_{t-1} \end{aligned} \quad (9)$$

These equations describe how to transform the dependent variable (Y) and the independent variables (X) for all observations from the second one onwards. Y_1^* is the transformed dependent variable at time t . It's calculated by subtracting $\hat{\rho}$ times the dependent variable at the previous time point $t-1$ from the original dependent variable at time t . X_1^* is the transformed independent variables at time t and it's calculated similarly to Y_1^* .

This transformation, known as quasi-differencing, removes the portion of each current value that is predictable from its immediate predecessor, effectively adjusting for serial correlation. The primary goal of this transformation is to eliminate serial correlation and ensure the errors in the transformed model are independent. The transformed model, which represents the regression model with the transformed variables, is as follows:

$$Y_t^* = X_t^*\beta + u_t, \quad (10)$$

where the new error term u_t is assumed to be white noise.

Because the actual autocorrelation coefficient, ρ , is typically unknown, GLSAR method employs an iterative process to find a reliable estimate. This means that every step discussed earlier is repeated until both $\hat{\rho}$ and β stabilize at their final values.

In summary, the process begins with an initial OLS regression on the original data, from which residuals are derived to provide a first approximation of $\hat{\rho}$, the estimated autocorrelation coefficient. Subsequently, a quasi-differencing transformation is applied to both the dependent variable (Y_t) and the independent variables (X_t) using this initial $\hat{\rho}$, resulting in transformed variables Y_t^* and X_t^* . An OLS regression is then performed on these transformed variables, leading to a refined set of residuals. From these new residuals, an updated estimate of $\hat{\rho}$ is calculated. This cycle of transformation and refitting is

repeated, with each iteration refining the estimates of both $\hat{\rho}$ and the regression coefficients, β . The process continues until these estimates converge to stable values, indicating that the model has adequately accounted for the serial correlation present in the data.

The formulas presented in this chapter describe the theoretical transformations that underline the statistical methodology implemented in Python, rather than direct computational procedures. The next chapter will present empirical results step by step, demonstrating the findings and the logic that guide us to the final model, GLSAR.

4. Empirical Results

The results of the study using the original dataset with the LOCF method are presented below:

Table 1. OLS summary (original dataset)

Metrics	ERIX (Renewable)	MSCI (Classic)
Covariance Type	Nonrobust	Nonrobust
Dependent Variable	ERIX (Renewable)	MSCI (Classic)
R-squared	0.641	0.691
Adj. R-squared	0.639	0.690
Method	Least Squares	Least Squares
F-statistic	454.0	570.0
Prob (F-statistic)	6.83e-280	9.73e-322
Log-Likelihood	-1160.2	-1063.3
AIC	2332	2139
BIC	2363	2170
No. Observations	1279	1279
Durbin-Watson	0.032	0.048
Omnibus Prob.	0.000	0.038
Jarque-Bera Prob.	2.95e-91	0.036
Mean Squared Error (MSE)	0.359	0.309
Correlation (R)	0.800	0.831

Source: Created by the authors

Table 1 outlines the outcomes from two ordinary least squares regressions, one using ERIX (Renewable) as the dependent variable and the other using MSCI (Classic). In each case, nonrobust covariance estimates are applied, and the analysis is based on a sample of 1279 observations using the least squares method. The R-squared values indicate that about 64% of the variation in ERIX (Renewable) and 69% in MSCI (Classic) are explained by the respective regressions. These models exhibit strong overall significance as evidenced by high F-statistics (454 and 570) and extremely low p-values, suggesting that the independent variables, taken as a whole, are statistically significant predictors of the outcomes. However, the validity of these results hinges on several critical assumptions intrinsic to the application of OLS (namely, the stationarity of the data, absence of autocorrelation, and homoscedasticity of the error terms). A notable issue arises with the Durbin-Watson statistics, which are exceedingly low (0.032 and 0.048), signaling severe positive autocorrelation among the residuals. Such a violation of the non-autocorrelation assumption can lead to biased standard errors and unreliable inference.

Furthermore, the diagnostic tests for normality, including the Omnibus and Jarque-Bera tests, hint at deviations from a normal distribution of residuals, particularly in the ERIX (Renewable) model. This deviation further complicates the inference process, as the reliability of OLS estimates partly depends on normally distributed errors. Additionally, the reported correlation, which is relatively high at 0.800 and 0.831 for the two models, suggests the possibility of multicollinearity. This multicollinearity could inflate the standard errors of the coefficient estimates and obscure the individual effects of the predictors.

Considering these factors, several diagnostic tests were conducted to ensure the reliability of the results and to guide necessary adjustments. One such test was the Augmented Dickey-Fuller (ADF) test, which examines whether a time series is stationary or exhibits nonstationarity. Stationarity means that a series has a constant mean, variance, and autocovariance over time (an essential condition for many time-series models, including OLS regression). If a variable is nonstationary, the relationships identified in the regression could be spurious, meaning they may appear statistically significant even when no meaningful connection exists. The ADF test thus helps us detect whether our variables require transformation to stabilize their statistical properties before being used in the analysis.

In parallel, the Variance Inflation Factor (VIF) test was employed to assess potential multicollinearity among the independent variables. Multicollinearity occurs when predictors are highly correlated with one another, which can inflate the variance of coefficient estimates and make it challenging to identify the unique effect of each predictor on the dependent variable. This can lead to unstable estimates and weaken the overall reliability of the model. By computing the VIF for each predictor, we can pinpoint which variables may be contributing redundant information.

Together, the ADF and VIF tests address two critical aspects of our data: ensuring that the time-series properties are appropriate for analysis and that the independent variables are not excessively collinear. Addressing nonstationarity helps us avoid spurious regression results, while managing multicollinearity enhances the precision and interpretability of the estimated coefficients. Ultimately, these tests ensure that our model's assumptions are met, thereby strengthening the robustness and credibility of the Ordinary Least Squares (OLS) estimates.

The results of these tests are presented in the tables below, providing a clearer understanding of the robustness of the OLS estimates.

Table 2. Test results: Augmented Dickey-Fuller (ADF) – original dataset

Variable	ADF Test Statistic	p.values	Critical Values (1%)	Critical Values (5%)	Critical Values (10%)
ERIX (Renewable)	-2.0520	0.2642	-3.4355	-2.8638	-2.5680
MSCI (Classic)	-1.3539	0.6042	-3.4355	-2.8638	-2.5680
Carbon_Future (Mar25)	-1.1849	0.6800	-3.4355	-2.8638	-2.5680
Allowance (EUAs EUAAs)	-1.1678	0.6873	-3.4355	-2.8638	-2.5680
GDP	-0.8904	0.7911	-3.4355	-2.8638	-2.5680
Inflation	-1.0430	0.7373	-3.4356	-2.8638	-2.5680
Interest Rate	1.3875	0.9971	-3.4356	-2.8638	-2.5680

Source: Created by the authors

The results of the Augmented Dickey-Fuller test (Table 2) consistently indicate that all variables in the dataset exhibit nonstationary behavior. The ADF test assesses whether a time series contains a unit root (a time series that has the tendency to wander and not return to its mean), which would imply nonstationarity. If the test statistic is more negative than the critical value at a given significance level, the null hypothesis of nonstationarity can be rejected in favor of stationarity. However, in this case, none of the variables meet that threshold.

For instance, the test statistic for ERIX (Renewable) is -2.0520, which does not surpass the critical values of -3.4355, -2.8638, and -2.5680 at the 1%, 5%, and 10% significance levels, respectively. Consequently, the null hypothesis cannot be rejected, suggesting that the series remains nonstationary. This conclusion is further reinforced by the p-value of 0.2642, which is well above conventional significance thresholds, indicating a high probability that the variable contains a unit root.

The same pattern emerges across all variables, with test statistics failing to exceed their respective critical values and p-values remaining considerably high. For example, MSCI (Classic) reports a test

statistic of -1.3539 with a p-value of 0.6042, and Carbon Futures (Mar25) has an even weaker test statistic of -1.1849 with a p-value of 0.6800. The Interest Rate variable is particularly notable, as its test statistic of 1.3875 is positive, making it the furthest from any critical threshold and confirming its strong nonstationary nature.

Given these results, it is evident that none of the variables are stationary in their current form. This has direct implications for econometric modeling, particularly for techniques such as Ordinary Least Squares (OLS), which require stationarity to produce valid estimates. Before proceeding with further analysis, transformations such as differencing or logarithmic adjustments should be considered to stabilize the time series and mitigate the risks associated with nonstationary data, such as spurious regression results. But in this case, logarithmic transformation should be avoided. The “interest_rate” variable contains periods with consistent zero values. This presents a critical problem because the logarithm function is undefined for zero ($\log(0)=-\infty$), leading to missing data points and potential computational errors. This would ultimately distort the transformed series, making it unsuitable for accurate analysis and possibly invalidating any subsequent modeling or forecasting efforts.

Table 3. Test results: Variance Inflation Factor (VIF) – original set

Variable	VIF
Carbon Future (Mar25)	10.3412
Allowance (EUAs_EUAs)	4.7123
GDP	4.9423
Inflation	6.7379
Interest Rate	2.3115

Source: Created by the authors

Table 3 provides insight into the level of multicollinearity among the independent variables used in the regression model. Carbon_Future (Mar25) exhibits a VIF of 10.3412, which exceeds the common threshold of 10, suggesting severe multicollinearity. This indicates that Carbon_Future (Mar25) is highly correlated with other predictors, making it difficult to isolate its individual effect on the dependent variable. In contrast, Allowance (EUAs_EUAs) and GDP have moderate VIF (4.7123 and 4.9423, respectively) while Inflation shows a higher, yet still moderate, VIF of 6.7379. Interest Rate, with a VIF of 2.3115, indicates minimal multicollinearity.

When Table 3 is considered alongside the Augmented Dickey-Fuller (ADF) test results (which consistently indicated non-stationarity among all variables) the need for data transformation becomes clear. The non-stationarity of the variables, as evidenced by the ADF test statistics and high p-values, signals that the original data series may lead to spurious regression results if used in levels. To address nonstationarity, the differencing method was applied to the variables originally reported at a daily frequency. Differencing is a common transformation in time-series analysis that removes trends by computing the change between consecutive observations, making the series stationary. This is particularly effective for financial and economic time series that often exhibit long-term trends or seasonality. However, variables originally reported at lower frequencies, such as monthly or annually, were standardized to a daily format using the Last Observation Carried Forward (LOCF) method. Applying simple differencing to these LOCF-adjusted variables would be inappropriate because consecutive daily values are identical until a new data point appears. This would introduce artificial zero differences and misleading volatility. Therefore, for LOCF-adjusted variables, an alternative approach is needed (one that preserves their inherent characteristics while ensuring stationarity).

A suitable solution involves using a rolling window transformation tailored to the variable’s original reporting frequency before differencing. For instance, daily variables (ERIX (Renewable), MSCI (Classic), and Carbon_Future (Mar25)) can be smoothed using a 30-day rolling window, which helps reduce short-term noise while capturing roughly monthly dynamics. For monthly variables (Inflation and Interest Rate), a 30-day window remains appropriate, since it corresponds to the original monthly frequency. Meanwhile, for annual variables (Allowance (EUAs_EUAs) and GDP), using a 365-day rolling window respects their natural reporting cycle.

By computing the rolling average over these windows and then applying the first difference, the series are transformed to better reflect the day-to-day changes in the underlying trend while mitigating nonstationarity. After these transformations, the daily series no longer display the flat segments characteristic of LOCF; instead, they reveal a more dynamic evolution of the original monthly or annual indicators.

The result of the ADF and VIF after the differencing are indicated in Table 4.

Table 4. ADF test results after differencing

Variable	p-value	Stationarity Status
ERIX (Renewable)	0.0000	Stationary after differencing
MSCI (Classic)	0.0000	Stationary after differencing
Carbon Future (Mar25)	0.0000	Stationary after differencing
Inflation	0.0002	Stationary after differencing
Interest Rate	0.0008	Stationary after differencing
Allowance (EUAs EUAAs)	0.5821	Still nonstationary after differencing
GDP	0.4401	Still nonstationary after differencing

Source: Created by the authors

The ADF test results indicate that differencing worked well for most variables. For the daily and monthly variables (ERIX (Renewable), MSCI (Classic), Carbon_Future (Mar25), Inflation, and Interest Rate) the p-values are essentially zero, confirming that these differenced series are stationary. In contrast, Allowance (EUAs EUAAs) and GDP remain nonstationary even after differencing, as their p-values (0.5821 and 0.4401, respectively) are not low enough to reject the null hypothesis of nonstationarity. This suggests that additional transformations may be necessary for these annual variables.

Table 5. Variance Inflation Factor (VIF) after differencing

Variable	VIF
Carbon Future (Mar25) diff	1.0601
Allowance (EUAs EUAAs) diff	1.4769
GDP diff	1.1355
Inflation diff	1.2274
Interest Rate diff	1.2529

Source: Created by the authors

Although Allowance (EUAs EUAAs) and GDP remain nonstationary, their VIF results are encouraging (Table 5), as all values are close to 1, indicating very low multicollinearity among the independent variables after transformation. With VIFs ranging from approximately 1.06 to 1.48, there is little risk that multicollinearity will distort the coefficient estimates in the regression model. While differencing has successfully addressed nonstationarity for the series, the annual variables (Allowance and GDP) require a different or additional transformation to achieve stationarity. Their nonstationarity can be a result of the nature of annual data, which tends to capture long-term trends, making it more likely to exhibit nonstationarity.

To address this problem, we applied the percentage change method, which computes the relative change between consecutive years. This transformation, also known as first differencing, removes long-term trends or growth patterns from the data, effectively stabilizing its variance. By applying this method, we were able to transform the annual variables into forms that fluctuate around a constant mean, making them stationary. After this transformation, the ADF test results showed significant improvement, with p-values for both variables dropping to 0.00, indicating that they were now stationary. The VIF test was computed once more time with the new transformed data and the results are presented in Table 6.

Table 6. Final test for VIF

Variable	VIF
const	1.247935
Carbon_Future(Mar25)_diff	1.027893
Inflation_diff	1.004258
Interest_Rate_diff	1.028383
Allowance(EUAs_EUAAs)_pct_change	1.002460
GDP_pct_change	1.001928

Source: Created by the authors

The analysis of the Variance Inflation Factor (VIF) results demonstrates a significant improvement in multicollinearity conditions within the dataset. The latest test reveals exceptionally low VIF values across all variables, with most clustering around 1. This indicates minimal multicollinearity among predictors, a desirable outcome for regression models as it ensures stable and reliable coefficient estimates. Notably, variables such as Carbon_Future(Mar25)_diff, Allowance(EUAs_EUAAs)_pct_change, and Inflation_diff exhibit values barely exceeding 1, suggesting negligible interaction or collinearity with other predictors.

A comparison with the previous VIF test further underscores these improvements. Every variable has experienced a reduction in its VIF, reflecting a clear decline in multicollinearity. The most notable change is observed for Allowance(EUAs_EUAAs)_diff, whose VIF has dropped from 1.4769 to 1.002460, effectively eliminating any collinearity concerns. Similarly, Inflation_diff and Interest_Rate_diff have each seen reductions of 0.22, reinforcing the improved independence among predictors. These adjustments enhance the overall model fit and ensure more reliable interpretations of the regression coefficients.

Regarding the constant term (const), its VIF remains slightly above 1, at 1.247935. In an ideal scenario where predictors are perfectly orthogonal, the constant's VIF would be exactly 1. However, minor correlations or data scaling effects can cause slight deviations. In this case, the marginal increase is insignificant and does not indicate any substantial collinearity issues, thus posing no threat to the model's integrity. Overall, these results strengthen the data's suitability for regression analysis, now that we dealt with the problems related to nonstationarity and multicollinearity.

The new dataset obtained was fit in an OLS model to check how the values changed after the transformations. Table 7 summarizes the OLS regression results for the transformed dataset, and these findings illustrate several key impacts of applying the differencing and percentage change transformation. In the original dataset, the models for ERIX (Renewable) and MSCI (Classic) showed high explanatory power with R-squared values around 0.64 and 0.69, respectively. However, after transformation, the R-squared values dropped sharply to 0.066 for ERIX and 0.107 for MSCI. This dramatic decline is expected with differencing, as it removes long-term trends and focuses on short-term variations, resulting in independent variables that now explain a much smaller portion of the variance in the dependent variables.

In addition to the decrease in explanatory power, the F-statistics for both models fell significantly (from 454.0 and 570.0 in the original models to 18.10 and 30.53 after transformation). Although the p-values remain extremely small, confirming that the models are statistically significant, the overall strength of the models has weakened considerably. The number of observations stayed nearly the same, ensuring that the transformation did not affect the dataset's length, yet the quality of the fit has clearly diminished.

Furthermore, the transformation has influenced other diagnostic measures. The original models displayed very low Durbin-Watson statistics, around 0.032 and 0.048, suggesting strong positive autocorrelation in the residuals. Post-transformation, the values improved slightly to 0.095 and 0.089, though they still hint at some remaining autocorrelation issues.

The AIC and BIC metrics also shifted; while the values for ERIX increased substantially, those for MSCI decreased, implying a nuanced impact on model complexity and fit. AIC (Akaike Information Criterion) and BIC (Bayesian Information Criterion) are statistical tools used to evaluate model quality

by balancing fit and complexity. Both prioritize models that better explain the data while penalizing excessive complexity or overfitting. A lower AIC or BIC value indicates a more efficient model that strikes the optimal balance between simplicity and explanatory power.

Table 7. OLS summary (transformed dataset)

Metric	ERIX (Renewable)	MSCI (Classic)
Dependent Variable	ERIX(Renewable) diff	MSCI(Classic) diff
R-squared	0.066	0.107
Adjusted R-squared	0.063	0.104
F-statistic	18.10	30.53
Prob (F-statistic)	2.20e-17	2.14e-29
Log-Likelihood	-4292.7	-561.29
No. Observations	1278	1278
AIC	8597.0	1135.0
BIC	8628.0	1165.0
Df Residuals	1272	1272
Mean Squared Error	48.4189	0.1409
Correlation (R)	0.2578	0.3273
Durbin-Watson	0.095	0.089
Omnibus Prob.	0.000	0.000
Jarque-Bera Prob.	1.15e-07	0.00
Kurtosis	3.669	8.509
Skew	-0.195	-1.318

Source: Created by the authors

However, the two differ in their approach to penalizing complexity. AIC penalizes complexity moderately, focusing more on minimizing information loss. BIC applies a stronger penalty for additional predictors, especially in larger datasets, favoring simpler models. After the transformation, the increase in AIC and BIC values for ERIX suggests a worsened balance of model complexity and fit, as its explanatory power diminished. In contrast, MSCI's decrease in AIC and BIC reflects an improvement, indicating that the transformation led to a better balance between simplicity and fit for this model. These shifts illustrate how transformations can differently impact models depending on their underlying structure and variables.

The tests for normality, such as the Jarque-Bera and Omnibus tests, reveal that departures from normality remain an issue in both cases. These mixed results highlight that while the transformation may address certain problems inherent in the original dataset, it does not resolve all issues.

To ensure the robustness of these findings, it is essential to further investigate the presence of autocorrelation and heteroscedasticity in the residuals. The heteroscedasticity problem must be thoroughly examined using the Breusch-Pagan Test. For autocorrelation, besides relying on the Durbin-Watson Test, the Breusch-Godfrey Test was also performed. Notably, the Durbin-Watson Test was checked again with a different code to confirm that the results are consistent with the tests from the OLS model in Python. These additional diagnostic tests will help ensure that the model's assumptions are not violated and that the inference drawn from the regression analysis remains valid. The results of the test are presented in Table 8.

Table 8 provides critical insights into the diagnostic tests for heteroscedasticity and autocorrelation in the regression models for ERIX (Renewable) and MSCI (Classic). The Breusch-Pagan test results indicate that both models suffer from heteroscedasticity. For ERIX, an LM statistic of 51.2091 with a p-value of 0.0000 strongly rejects the null hypothesis of constant error variance, while MSCI's LM statistic of 23.4609 with a p-value of 0.0003 leads to a similar conclusion. These low p-values, coupled with significant F-statistics, confirm that the variance of the residuals is not uniform across the dataset, which could bias standard error estimates and undermine the reliability of statistical inferences.

Table 8 - Heteroscedasticity and Autocorrelation test results for ERIX (Renewable) and MSCI (Classic)

Test Type	Statistic	ERIX (Renewable)	MSCI (Classic)
Breusch-Pagan Test (Heteroscedasticity)	LM statistic	51.2091	23.4609
	p-value	0.0000	0.0003
	F-statistic	10.6193	4.7575
	F p-value	0.0000	0.0003
Durbin-Watson Test (Autocorrelation)	Durbin-Watson statistic	0.0948 (Ideal \approx 2)	0.0886 (Ideal \approx 2)
Breusch-Godfrey Test (Autocorrelation)	LM statistic	1163.0021	1168.3136
	p-value	0.0000	0.0000
	F-statistic	2562.6965	2699.0637
	F p-value	0.0000	0.0000

Source: Created by the authors

Turning to autocorrelation, the Durbin-Watson statistics for both models are far from the ideal value of approximately 2. Such low values clearly indicate strong positive autocorrelation, suggesting that the residuals are highly correlated rather than independent. This autocorrelation can reduce the efficiency of the regression estimates, making the coefficients less reliable. The Breusch-Godfrey test further corroborates this issue, with LM statistics exceeding 1163 for both models and corresponding p-values of 0.0000. The extremely high F-statistics and their p-values confirm that the null hypothesis of no autocorrelation is decisively rejected.

These findings have important implications. The presence of heteroscedasticity means that the assumption of constant error variance is violated, which can compromise hypothesis tests and the accuracy of confidence intervals. The detected autocorrelation, evidenced by both the Durbin-Watson and Breusch-Godfrey tests, signals that the residuals are correlated over time.

Considering these results, the OLS model is no longer a suitable method to assess the impact of the independent variables on the dependent variables because it fails to address key violations of classical regression assumptions (specifically, heteroskedasticity and autocorrelation). In our initial (transformed dataset) OLS analysis, the residuals exhibited severe autocorrelation, as reflected in a Durbin-Watson statistic of merely 0.095 for ERIX (Renewable) and 0.089 for MSCI (Classic). Moreover, heteroskedasticity was evident, with the LM tests yielding a statistic of approximately 51.21 ($p \approx 7.84 \times 10^{-10}$) for ERIX and 23.46 ($p \approx 0.0002755$) for MSCI. These figures indicate that the error variances are not constant, and that residuals are highly correlated, which in turn undermines the reliability of standard errors and the statistical significance of our estimates.

To overcome these challenges, we first attempted to switch to a Generalized Least Squares (GLS) model with robust covariance adjustments (HC0) and then to a Weighted Least Squares (WLS) approach. The GLS with robust covariance produced nearly identical coefficient estimates as the OLS (with R-squared values of 0.066 for ERIX and 0.107 for MSCI, and F-statistics of 19.07 and 29.61 respectively), but the Durbin-Watson statistics remained extremely low at 0.095 and 0.089. The robust GLS approach adjusted the standard errors for heteroscedasticity, but failed to eliminate it, and did nothing to mitigate the autocorrelation, which continued to violate the assumption of error independence. Therefore, this approach was insufficient.

Subsequently, we employed WLS to address heteroscedasticity by down-weighting observations with higher variance. The initial WLS results for both ERIX and MSCI were essentially identical to those from the GLS model, retaining the problematic Durbin-Watson values of 0.095 and 0.089. In a refined WLS attempt, the R-squared for ERIX unrealistically inflated to 1.000 and for MSCI to 0.985, and the coefficient estimates became extremely significant. This dramatic increase in R-squared, while attempting to correct for heteroscedasticity, highlights the model's sensitivity and potential for overfitting. However, despite these seemingly improved fit statistics, the Durbin-Watson values only modestly increased to 0.311 for ERIX and 0.365 for MSCI, while the LM heteroscedasticity tests still confirmed significant heteroscedasticity (LM statistic of 51.258 for ERIX and 23.453 for MSCI with p-

values in the order of 10^{-10} and 10^{-4} respectively). These outcomes confirmed that WLS failed to adequately remedy the complex heteroscedasticity present and did not resolve the serial correlation among residuals.

Given that our primary objective is to accurately assess the impact of the independent variables (X) on the dependent variables (Y), it is critical to obtain unbiased coefficient estimates with reliable standard errors. Autocorrelation, which severely undermined these properties in our OLS, GLS, and WLS approaches, had to be explicitly addressed. This led us to adopt a Feasible Generalized Least Squares (FGLS) approach using the GLSAR method.

In implementing FGLS, we started by standardizing the independent variables and adding a constant to improve interpretability and numerical stability. We then performed an initial OLS regression to obtain residuals, from which we estimated the autocorrelation coefficient (ρ) using the autocorrelation function (ACF). This estimated “ ρ ” was then incorporated into the GLSAR model. The iterative fitting mechanism of GLSAR adjusted the covariance structure of the error terms to account for the serial correlation.

The impact of this approach is evident in the FGLS results presented in Table 9.

Table 9. GLSAR regressions for ERIX (Renewable) and MSCI (Classic)

Dependent Variable	ERIX (Renewable)_diff	MSCI (Classic)_diff
R-squared	0.024	0.076
Adj. R-squared	0.020	0.072
Method	Least Squares	Least Squares
F-statistic	6.179	20.90
Prob (F-statistic)	1.14e-05	4.06e-20
Log-Likelihood	-2642.9	1014.0
No. Observations	1277	1277
AIC	5298	-2016
Df Residuals	1271	1271
BIC	5329	-1985
Covariance Type	Nonrobust	Nonrobust
Durbin-Watson	1.818	1.908
Omnibus	141.137	348.138
Prob(Omnibus)	0.000	0.000
Jarque-Bera (JB)	1069.807	5771.067
Skew	0.166	0.808
Prob(JB)	4.95e-233	0.00
Kurtosis	7.472	13.288
Cond. No.	41.2	33.7

Source: Created by the authors

For ERIX, the GLSAR regression results show an R-squared of 0.024 and an adjusted R-squared of 0.020. This means that only about 2–2.4% of the variance in ERIX (Renewable)_diff is explained by the independent variables (a rather low figure, but this outcome is acceptable when our primary interest is in assessing the impact of specific predictors rather than achieving a high overall explanatory power). The F-statistic of 6.179 (with a p-value of 1.14×10^{-5}) confirms that, despite the low R-squared, the model is statistically significant overall.

Similarly, for MSCI, the R-squared is 0.076 with an adjusted R-squared of 0.072, indicating that around 7–7.6% of the variance is explained by the model. The higher F-statistic of 20.90 (p-value of 4.06×10^{-20}) supports the statistical significance of the model for MSCI, even though, again, the overall explanatory power remains low.

Both models were estimated using the least squares method, but the key innovation here is the use of GLSAR to adjust for autocorrelation. In both cases, the covariance type is reported as "Nonrobust,"

meaning that the standard errors are based on the model’s internal assumptions about the error covariance structure rather than additional robust adjustments. This is typical for GLSAR output once the autocorrelation has been explicitly modelled.

One of the most noticeable improvements is seen in the Durbin–Watson statistics. For ERIX, the Durbin–Watson value is 1.818, and for MSCI, it is 1.908. Values much closer to the ideal of 2, compared to the extremely low values seen in earlier OLS and WLS models. These values indicate that the serial correlation in the residuals has been substantially mitigated.

The diagnostic tests for residual normality, however, still point to some issues. The Omnibus tests yield statistics of 141.137 for ERIX and 348.138 for MSCI, with both p-values essentially zero. Similarly, the Jarque-Bera tests are very high (1069.807 for ERIX and 5771.067 for MSCI), with associated p-values effectively 0, indicating significant departures from a normal distribution. The skewness values (0.166 for ERIX and 0.808 for MSCI) suggest that the residuals for MSCI are more positively skewed. Additionally, the kurtosis values (7.472 for ERIX and 13.288 for MSCI) are much higher than the normal kurtosis value of 3, which suggests that the residuals have heavy tails.

Other metrics include the log-likelihood, which is -2642.9 for ERIX and 1014.0 for MSCI, and model selection criteria such as AIC (5298 for ERIX and -2016 for MSCI) and BIC (5329 for ERIX and -1985 for MSCI). These figures provide a basis for comparing models, though in our case the focus is primarily on the reliability of the coefficient estimates in the presence of autocorrelation.

Lastly, the condition numbers (41.2 for ERIX and 33.7 for MSCI) indicate that while multicollinearity has increased compared to the transformed OLS models, this increase is a result of the different estimation method used in GLSAR. The iterative process of Generalized Least Squares, which accounts for autocorrelation, can introduce some degree of dependency among regressors, leading to higher condition numbers. However, these values remain well below the conventional threshold of 100, suggesting that multicollinearity is not severe enough to undermine the reliability of the coefficient estimates.

While the diagnostic results confirm that the GLSAR models effectively mitigate autocorrelation, they do not fully address heteroscedasticity or deviations from normality. Consequently, although the statistical validity of the models improves in terms of serial correlation correction, to gain deeper insights, we now turn to the estimated coefficients, their corresponding t-statistics, and significance levels. By examining these values, we can determine the relative impact of carbon futures, EUAs/EUAAs, macroeconomic variables, and regulatory factors on the stock returns of renewable and traditional energy companies.

Table 10 presents a detailed comparison of the estimated coefficients for the ERIX and MSCI models, allowing us to assess the magnitude and direction of these relationships, as well as their statistical significance.

Table 10. Comparison of coefficients, t-statistics, and significance for ERIX and MSCI Models (GLSAR)

Variable	ERIX Coefficient (t-stat, p-value)	MSCI Coefficient (t-stat, p-value)
Carbon Future(Mar25)	0.7068 (t: 4.416, p-value: 0.000)	0.0931 (t: 10.172, p-value: 0.000)
Inflation	-0.4657 (t: -1.962, p-value: 0.050)	0.0137 (t: 1.011, p-value: 0.312)
Interest Rate	0.5454 (t: 2.555, p-value: 0.011)	0.0076 (t: 0.623, p-value: 0.533)
Allowance(EUAs_EUAs)	-0.0294 (t: -0.757, p-value: 0.449)	0.0012 (t: 0.528, p-value: 0.598)
GDP	0.0099 (t: 0.254, p-value: 0.800)	-0.0030 (t: -1.365, p-value: 0.172)

Source: Created by the authors

Table 10 presents a detailed comparison of the estimated coefficients, t-statistics, and p-values for the ERIX and MSCI, allowing us to assess the impact of each independent variable on the dependent variables. The coefficients for Carbon_Future and Interest_Rate are significant in the ERIX model, with

Carbon_Future exhibiting a particularly strong impact. For MSCI, only the Carbon_Future coefficient is statistically significant, though its magnitude is smaller than in the ERIX model. The remaining variables (Inflation, Allowance, and GDP) do not show significant impacts in the MSCI or in the ERIX model. This detailed comparison underscores that while some factors consistently influence renewable energy stocks, the impact of these variables on classic energy indices is generally weaker or statistically insignificant.

To further illustrate the relationships between the independent variables and the dependent variables, a correlation matrix provides a useful visual representation of their associations. By examining the strength and direction of these correlations, we can gain additional insights into potential multicollinearity issues and the underlying dynamics between predictors and stock prices, as shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1. Heatmap correlation matrix

Source: Created by the authors

In contrast to the findings from Table 10, the correlation matrix (figure 1), which captures the unadjusted bivariate relationships between variables, shows that the correlation between ERIX and Carbon_Future is only 0.02, while with MSCI it is 0.26. At first glance, these values appear at odds with the regression findings. However, correlation coefficients do not account for the influence of other variables (they measure the raw association between two variables without any control for confounding factors). This is why a variable like Carbon_Future might show a very low correlation with ERIX in a simple bivariate sense yet have a strong, significant coefficient in the regression model; the regression isolates the unique effect of Carbon_Future on ERIX after controlling for Inflation, Interest_Rate, Allowance, and GDP.

Similarly, while Interest_Rate has a correlation of -0.24 with ERIX, its regression coefficient is positive (0.5454) and statistically significant. This discrepancy suggests that the relationship between Interest_Rate and ERIX is more complex and is influenced by the presence of other predictors in the model. Multivariate regression captures these conditional relationships, which can differ markedly from the simple correlations presented in the matrix.

Overall, the differences between the correlation matrix and the regression results arise because the correlation matrix shows the overall, unadjusted pairwise relationships, whereas the regression coefficients reflect the partial, or net, effects of each variable. The regression analysis reveals the true impact of each predictor on the dependent variables once the interrelationships among predictors are considered.

5. Conclusions

The objective of this research was to evaluate the impact of carbon futures, allowance actioned or sold EUAs/EUAs and macroeconomic variables on the stock prices of renewable (ERIX) and traditional (MSCI) energy companies. Through a comprehensive empirical approach, beginning with OLS regressions on the original dataset, followed by careful transformation of nonstationary variables, and culminating in the application of Feasible Generalized Least Squares (FGLS) via the GLSAR method, the study made significant strides in addressing key econometric challenges.

One of the primary achievements was the effective handling of autocorrelation. The initial OLS models exhibited severe autocorrelation, as evidenced by very low Durbin–Watson statistics, which cast doubt on the reliability of the coefficient estimates. By switching to FGLS with the GLSAR method, the serial independence of the residuals was notably improved, with Durbin–Watson values moving closer to the ideal value of 2. This improvement bolstered confidence in the subsequent analysis of how the independent variables influenced energy indices.

The regression analysis further revealed insightful differences between the two models. Carbon futures emerged as a significant driver in both the ERIX and MSCI models, exerting a particularly strong influence on renewable energy stock. In contrast, other macroeconomic variables such as inflation, interest rate, allowance, and GDP displayed limited or statistically insignificant effects. These findings suggest that renewable energy stocks might be more sensitive to market expectations captured by carbon futures compared to traditional energy stocks. The contrasting results between the simple correlation matrix and the multivariate regression coefficients underscored the importance of controlling for confounding factors. While bivariate correlations might have indicated weak associations, the regression analysis clarified the conditional relationships, revealing the true impact of each predictor once other variables were accounted for.

Despite successfully mitigating autocorrelation, persistent challenges remain in the form of heteroscedasticity and non-normality in the model residuals. Two main factors appear to contribute to these issues. First, the dataset comprises variables reported at different frequencies (daily for stock indices and carbon futures, monthly, and annually for the rest). Daily data inherently exhibit higher volatility and more pronounced distributional anomalies, such as heavy tails and skewness, while monthly or annual data are generally more stable. When these data are combined in a single model, the differing characteristics naturally lead to non-constant error variances and deviations from normality. Second, to transform lower-frequency data into a daily format, the Last Observation Carried Forward (LOCF) method was employed. Although LOCF creates artificial flat segments (which can disrupt the independence of observations and introduce sudden jumps) it was chosen because the macroeconomic indicators (such as European Union GDP, Inflation Rate, and Eurozone Interest Rate Decision) do not naturally fluctuate daily. Alternative approaches risked introducing artificial trends or values that could potentially undermine the true impact of the independent variables on stock prices. Nonetheless, we acknowledge that LOCF is not ideal for least squares regression models, and even with subsequent adjustments, the models remain sensitive to these methodological limitations.

These persistent challenges mean that while the coefficient estimates derived from the GLSAR approach offer valuable insights into the dynamics of energy stock prices, caution must be exercised when interpreting standard errors and confidence intervals. Future research could benefit from exploring alternative modelling techniques, such as robust regression methods that employ heteroscedasticity-consistent covariance matrix estimators, or by adopting mixed-frequency models that better integrate data with differing periodicities. Additionally, enhanced transformation methods that capture the unique volatility and distributional characteristics of high-frequency versus low-frequency data might help alleviate the issues observed.

Conflicts of Interest

The authors declare that there are no conflicts of interest regarding the publication of this paper.

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